

Photon will get the charge and mass with circling motion in loop

FU WEI*

**fuwei-opto@foxmail.com*

Affiliation: A Private Member, XingHaiMingCheng, Shenzhen, 518052, CHINA

Abstract: When a photon travels in line, it is only an energy unit without the charge and rest mass. But if it circles in loop based on some conditions, this photon will get the mass and charge the same with matter particle. Just by changing the frequency or polarization mode of this circling photon, all kinds of matter particles can be produced by this motion of photon. This conclusion has been deduced and calculated in this paper. Some new predictions and equations about photon and matter particles were also given.

Main text

1. Forward

In our present physical theory, people always take it for granted that the electron is a point with the charge and mass, which appears as a probability wave around the nucleus to form the electron cloud. We can use the equations to describe the orbit of the electron and the magnetic moment produced by the electron spinning. But we still can't answer why in the micro world, sometimes matter particles don't follow the classical electromagnetic theory, but sometimes they become to follow the classical electromagnetic theory.

For example, when the electrons is accelerated in a ring accelerator, they will follow the classical theory to emit energy, but when the electrons circle in atom, they will not follow the classical theory and never radiate energy at all. When the electrons circle along the orbit, they will follow the classical theory to produce the orbital magnetic moment. At the same time, the electron itself can carry the spin magnetic moment even its own radius is almost zero, which does not follow the classical theory.

Our current physical theory can't explain and predict these phenomena well. So that when we use higher and higher energy to open up more and more micro world, the prediction becomes more and more difficult. The reason for these problems may be caused by our misunderstanding about the matter wave.

We all think that matter wave is the probability for matter particles to appear in space, that means both the mass and charge of a matter particle move as a point in the matter wave. But we ignored another possibility about matter wave: there is no matter particles in the world at all, all the elementary matter particles are just formed by a corresponding electromagnetic wave circling with different frequency and polarization mode.

Next, we will analyze the details about this possibility. Under this possibility, the elementary matter particle, which formed by electromagnetic wave, will be able to get the fixed charge, mass and wave-particle duality.

2. Circling motion of photon

Light is the electromagnetic wave that is consisted by lots of photons. So when a single photon travels, it can also be considered as a tiny electromagnetic wave, which has the characteristics of electromagnetic amplitude, frequency, wavelength, wave number, momentum and energy.

First, let's do a thought experiment to make this photon polarized linearly. This time, its electric field intensity(E) is:

$$E = A \cos(\omega t - kz) , \omega = 2\pi/T , k = 2\pi/\lambda$$

“A” is the max amplitude of electric field intensity, “T” is the cycle of the photon, “ λ ” is the wavelength.

Fig.1. Circling Photon

As shown with Figure 1, then let's give this photon a centripetal acceleration to make it circle in loop(Radius = R) by the head to end of all its waves. This time, the value of this centripetal acceleration will determine the value of loop radius. But the angular momentum(L) of this photon will not be changed even if the centripetal acceleration value are changed in the future because the centripetal acceleration just points the loop center. Then:

$$L = P * R = \frac{h}{\lambda} R$$

$$R/\lambda = L/h \text{ -----(1)}$$

In this loop, according to the Poynting Theorem, the energy flux density(\vec{S}) at every points is:

$$\vec{S} = \vec{E} \times \vec{H} , \vec{E} \perp \vec{H} , \sqrt{\mu}H = \sqrt{\epsilon}E$$

So the average energy flux density(\vec{S}_{av}) at every points is:

$$\vec{S}_{av} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \vec{E}(t) \times \vec{H}(t) dt = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon}{\mu}} A^2 \cos^2(\omega t - kz) dt = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon}{\mu}} A^2$$

And its direction is kept to circle along the loop. The energy(ξ) of this circling photon is:

$$\xi = S_{av} * T_c = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} A^2 * \frac{2\pi R}{c} = A^2 R \frac{\pi}{c} \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} \text{ -----(2)}$$

“ T_c ” is the time for this photon to circle a whole loop. At the same time, the photon energy can also be expressed as:

$$\xi = h\nu = hc / \lambda$$

Substitute equation 2 to the above equation:

$$A^2 R \frac{\pi}{c} \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} = \frac{hc}{\lambda}$$

$$A^2 R^2 \frac{\pi}{c} \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} = \frac{R}{\lambda} hc$$

$$AR = c \sqrt{\frac{R}{\lambda} * \frac{h}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\varepsilon}}} \text{ -----(3)}$$

Substitute equation 1 to equation 3:

$$AR = c \sqrt{\frac{L}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\varepsilon}}} \text{ -----(4)}$$

Summarized, when a polarized photon circle in loop just caused by a centripetal acceleration and all its waves are connected by the head to end, then:

- ① Its angular momentum(L) will not be changed.
- ② This loop radius is proportional to the wavelength of circling photon.(Equation 1)
- ③ This loop radius is inversely proportional to the energy of circling photon.
- ④ This loop radius is inversely proportional to the electric field intensity amplitude of circling photon.(Equation 4).

3. Polarization producing charge

3.1 Negative charge

Case 1:

In this case, if that circling photon above is polarized to keep its electric vibration always in the loop plane, and its lower electrical potential points of the electric field intensity vibrating in physics are distributed on both sides of the central axis(z axis), as shown in Figure.2.a.

Fig.2.a

Fig.2.b.

Fig.2.c.

Fig.2. Negative charge

This time, because of the compression caused by loop to space, the electric field intensity pointing to the loop center becomes more intensive than that pointing outside at each point on loop in every cycle of this photon, as shown in Figure.2.b.

Then, as shown in Figure.2.c, every quarter cycle ($\frac{T}{4}$) for the electric field intensity to point outside the loop, is stretched to $\frac{T}{4} * \frac{\pi/2 + \beta_1}{\pi/2}$, and every quarter cycle ($\frac{T}{4}$) for the electric field intensity to point inside the loop, is compressed to $\frac{T}{4} * \frac{\pi/2 - \beta_1}{\pi/2}$.

So the average electric field intensity pointing outside (\bar{E}_{out}) at each point of loop is reduced:

$$\bar{E}_{out} = \frac{1}{\frac{T}{4}(\frac{\pi}{2} + \beta_1) / \frac{\pi}{2}} \int_0^{\frac{T}{4}} A \cos(\omega t - kz) dt = \frac{2A}{\pi + 2\beta_1}$$

Similarly, the average electric intensity pointing inside(\bar{E}_{in}) at each point of loop is increased:

$$\bar{E}_{in} = \frac{1}{\frac{T}{4}(\frac{\pi}{2} - \beta_1) / \frac{\pi}{2}} \int_0^{\frac{T}{4}} A \cos(\omega t - kz) dt = \frac{2A}{\pi - 2\beta_1}$$

At last, an average electric field intensity pointing to loop center will be generated at each point on the loop:

$$\Delta \bar{E} = \bar{E}_{in} - \bar{E}_{out} = \frac{2A}{\pi - 2\beta_1} - \frac{2A}{\pi + 2\beta_1} \text{ -----(5)}$$

In Figure.2.c, the value of β_2 is determined by the waves number of the photon in loop.

$$4\beta_2 = \frac{\lambda}{R}$$

$$\beta_2 = \frac{\lambda}{4R}$$

$$\because \beta_1 + \alpha = \beta_2 + \alpha = \frac{\pi}{2}$$

$$\therefore \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \frac{\lambda}{4R}$$

Substitute the above equation to equation 5:

$$\Delta \bar{E} = \bar{E}_{in} - \bar{E}_{out} = \frac{2A}{\pi - 2\beta_1} - \frac{2A}{\pi + 2\beta_1} = \frac{2A\lambda / R}{\pi^2 - \lambda^2 / 4R^2}$$

It means the electric flux density(D_l) pointing to the loop center is produced at every point of this closed loop.

$$D_l = \epsilon * \Delta \bar{E} = \frac{2\epsilon A \lambda / R}{\pi^2 - \lambda^2 / 4R^2}$$

When the loop rotates on the axis of its diameter, on the closed surface of this sphere, the sum of all the electric flux pointing to the sphere center will generate a negative charge inside of loop. The value of this charge is:

$$q = \oint_s D ds = - \oint_{2\pi R} D_l dl = -4\pi \epsilon A R * \frac{\lambda / R}{\pi^2 - \lambda^2 / 4R^2}$$

Substitute equation 3 to the above equation:

$$q = -4\pi \epsilon \sqrt{\frac{R}{\lambda} * \frac{h}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\epsilon}}} * \frac{\lambda / R}{\pi^2 - \lambda^2 / 4R^2} \text{ -----(6)}$$

In fact, π^2 is much bigger than $\lambda^2 / 4R^2$, for easy to calculate:

$$q \approx -4\pi\epsilon \sqrt{\frac{R}{\lambda} * \frac{h}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\epsilon}}} * \frac{\lambda/R}{\pi^2}$$

Substitute equation 1 to the above equation:

$$q \approx -4\epsilon c \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{R} * \frac{h}{\pi^3} \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\epsilon}}} = -4\epsilon c h \sqrt{\frac{1}{\pi^3 L} \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\epsilon}}}$$

In this thought experiment, if we want to make the photon loop get a charge the same with the electron charge, we just need to give it a fixed angular momentum, or a fixed ratio of the loop radius to photon wavelength. This needed ratio can be calculated from the above equation:

$$\frac{R}{\lambda} \approx \frac{16\epsilon^2 c^2 h}{\pi^3 q_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\epsilon}}, \quad q_e \approx -1.6 \times 10^{-19} C$$

$$\frac{R}{\lambda} \approx \frac{16\epsilon^2 c^2 h}{\pi^3 q_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\epsilon}} = 35.6$$

$$\therefore \frac{2\pi R}{\lambda} \approx 223.7$$

From the thought experiment, the loop circumference ($2\pi R$) should be an integral multiples of the wavelength. So the ratio ($2\pi R / \lambda$) should be an integer approaching 223. Substitute $n = 2\pi R / \lambda = 222, 223$ or 224 into equation 6 to calculate and check the accurate charge value.

$$q = -4\pi\epsilon \sqrt{\frac{R}{\lambda} * \frac{h}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\epsilon}}} * \frac{\lambda/R}{\pi^2 - \lambda^2 / 4R^2} = -\frac{4\epsilon c}{\pi(1-1/n^2)} \sqrt{\frac{2h}{n} \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\epsilon}}}, \quad n = 222, 223 \text{ or } 224$$

$$\therefore c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mu\epsilon}}$$

$$\therefore q = -\frac{4}{\pi(1-1/n^2)} \sqrt{\frac{2hc\epsilon}{n}}$$

$$q = -1.6033 \times 10^{-19} C, \quad n=222$$

$$q = -1.5997 \times 10^{-19} C, \quad n=223$$

$$q = -1.5961 \times 10^{-19} C, \quad n=224$$

In order to keep photon loop getting a charge closer to the measured electron charge in fact, the ratio ($n = 2\pi R / \lambda$) is modified to an integer 222.

So in this photon loop:

$$L = P * R = \frac{h}{\lambda} R = \frac{h}{2\pi} * \frac{2\pi R}{\lambda} = \frac{111h}{\pi}, \quad q = -1.6033 \times 10^{-19} C$$

That's to say, if we can make a single photon circle with a fixed angular momentum ($\frac{111h}{\pi}$) by the head to end, and polarize it based on Case1, it will get a fixed negative charge the same with an electron. No matter how its loop radius, wavelength, and energy are changed by the centripetal acceleration in the future, its charge will never be changed.

3.2 Positive Charge

Case 2:

Similarly with Case 1, if the circling photon is polarized to keep its electric vibration always in the loop plane, but its higher electrical potential points of the electric field intensity vibrating in physics are distributed on both sides of the central axis(z axis), as shown in Figure.3.a.

Fig.3. Positive Charge

This time, because of the compression caused by loop to space, the electric field intensity pointing outside become more intensive than that pointing inside at each point of loop, as shown in Figure.3.b.

This imbalance in electric field intensity will create a charge just like case 1, but it is a positive charge. The charge value can be calculated by the same method:

$$Q = \frac{4}{\pi(1-1/n^2)} \sqrt{\frac{2hc\varepsilon}{n}} = 1.6033 \times 10^{-19} C \quad , n=222.$$

3.3 No charge

Case 3:

If the circling photon is polarized in this case that its electric vibration is kept vertical to the loop plane, as shown in Figure 4. In this case, no charge will be shown in the loop because the electric field intensity of this photon is balanced on the different directions.

Fig.4. No Charge

4. Velocity, Energy, Inertia and Mass

The loop formed by circling photon can also get inertia and mass. First, let's continue with another thought experiment similar with that in the Special Relativity.

Fig.5. Velocity Changing Energy

As shown in Figure 5.a, the circumference of photon loop is l . When the loop moves at velocity v along the x -axis, the velocity of photon circling on the loop is still c , which cannot be changed. This makes the actual journey of electromagnetic wave become an unclosed spiral trajectory in reference frame $x-t$, as shown in Figure 5.b. But in the reference frame $(r-\theta)$ which is together with loop centroid, as shown in Figure 5.c, the journey of electromagnetic wave is still an closed loop, but the circumference of this loop becomes l' in reference frame $x-t$, and this whole loop moves a straight distance $v \cdot t$ in reference frame $x-t$. " t " is time for this photon to circle a whole loop in reference frame $x-t$.

Fig.6.the Mass of Loop

For easy to calculate, as shown in Figure 6, l and l' are drawn into straight lines.

$$l'^2 + v^2 t^2 = c^2 t^2$$

$$l' = ct\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$$

$$l' = l\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$$

While the whole loop moves, the loop circumference is shortened, but the waves number on loop is not changed, so that its wavelength(λ') is shortened together, $\lambda' = \lambda_0\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$

Then its frequency and energy(ξ') increases:

$$\xi' = \xi_0/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$$

ξ_0 is the energy of this loop at rest. λ_0 is the wavelength of photon loop at rest. The increased energy due to the velocity v of moving loop is the kinetic energy of the loop:

$$\xi_K = \xi' - \xi_0 = \xi_0 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} - 1 \right)$$

According to the Special Relativity, a object with the mass($m_0 = \xi_0/c^2$) can get the kinetic energy($\xi_0 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} - 1 \right)$) due to its velocity(v). It means this photon loop gets the inertia and rest mass. The value of this mass corresponds to ξ_0 .

$$m_0 = \frac{\xi_0}{c^2} = \frac{h\nu_0}{c^2} = \frac{h}{c\lambda_0}$$

Any change in velocity will directly cause the energy changed in this loop. The loop structure can cause energy to generate inertia and mass against any change of velocity to make itself maintain inertia naturally and do uniform linear motion without external force.

5. The Conclusion

In this paper, the following conclusions can be drawn from these thought experiments:

If a photon circles in loop by the head to end with a fixed angular momentum($\frac{11h}{\pi}$) based on any case in this paper caused by a centripetal acceleration, then

① The frequency of this circling photon determines the loop mass: $m_0 = h\nu_0/c^2$.

② The polarization mode of this circling photon makes the loop generate a fixed charges with different polarity(+/-/0). The charge value will never be changed:

$$q = \frac{4}{\pi(1-1/222^2)} \sqrt{\frac{hc\varepsilon}{111}} \approx \frac{4}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{hc\varepsilon}{111}}.$$

③ This loop will show the wave-particle duality. The particle characteristic will be shown by the charge centroid, while the wave characteristic will be shown by the circling electromagnetic wave.

6. The Hypothesis and Prediction

When a photon with 2.43×10^{-12} m wavelength and 511 Kev energy is polarized and circles based on Case1, this loop will show the charge and mass the same with an electron. When this loop rotates on the axis of its diameter, it will be completely same as an electron cloud. So that we can assume that the electron cloud is just produced by this photon loop. This time, the mass and charge of the electron are distributed in the whole loop, not in a point. So the electron loop can produce the spin magnetic moment.

Similarly, when a photon with 2.43×10^{-12} m wavelength and 511 Kev energy is polarized and circles based on Case2, this loop will show the charge and mass the same with a positron.

If we increase the centripetal acceleration for this “positron loop” to reduce its wavelength to 1.32×10^{-15} m, its loop radius will be reduced to 1/1836, its energy will increase to 0.938 Gev, and its mass will also be increased to 1836 times. This time, this “positron loop” in high energy state will get the same charge and mass with a proton.

When a photon with 0.939 Gev energy is polarized and circles based on Case3, this loop will show the charge and mass the same with a neutron.

Any other particle characteristic of matter can also be produced by a circling photon with different wavelength and polarization mode.

So a hypothesis can be given that any elementary particle of matter is a corresponded photon carrying the centripetal acceleration to circle in loop by the head to end with a fixed angular momentum ($\frac{111h}{\pi}$). This hypothesis can explain well why the matter particles can keep mass, charge and how the energy converts among light, matter and velocity.

This hypothesis also provides some understandable physical means for quantum mechanics. The following quantum phenomenon can be explained by classical physics.

① Why the "electron" surrounding the nucleus never leaks energy and falls into the nucleus? In this hypothesis, it is only the electromagnetic wave circling around the nucleus, the charge is not surrounding with it, but stay in the loop.

② As a point particle, the quantum spin just can be described as an intrinsic property with no reason in present quantum mechanics. And more incredible thing is that the smaller “electron” in present theories can produce much bigger spin magnetic moments than protons. In this hypothesis, all the particles are the loops, and the loop radius allows them spinning to generate the magnetic moments. And because the loop radius of electron is much larger than that of proton, the magnetic moment of electron loop spin is certainly much larger than that of proton.

This hypothesis is amazing, but the process of deduction and calculation is firmly followed to the logic and proven physical theory. So if the centripetal acceleration really exists in nature which captures photon to circle, the hypothesis should be true.

Therefore, the following predictions can be given to check whether this centripetal acceleration really exists and whether the matter particle is made of photon with circling motion by the targeted experiments:

① Even if an electron leaves the nucleus, it should still keep the centripetal acceleration to circle around a center. The relationship between the radius(R) of this circling motion and the mass(m)/ energy(ξ)/ wavelength(λ) of this electron should follow the equations:

$$mR = \frac{h}{c\lambda} R = \frac{L}{c} = \frac{111h}{\pi c}, \quad \xi R = mc^2 R = \frac{111hc}{\pi}$$

For example, if an electron stays in a hydrogen atom with a loop radius of $0.53 \times 10^{-10} m$, its wavelength should be $1.50 \times 10^{-12} m$, its energy should be 828Kev, and its mass should be $14.7 \times 10^{-31} kg$. But if it leaves the nucleus and becomes a free electron with 511Kev, it will still keep circling motion around a center where even there is nothing, at this time its loop radius should be changed to $0.86 \times 10^{-10} m$, its wavelength should be increased to $2.43 \times 10^{-12} m$, and its mass should be reduced to $9.1 \times 10^{-31} kg$. This prediction should be proven by the classical scattering experiment, but it should be noted that the high energy particle cannot be used as the detecting particle. If the electron with 20Gev is used as the detecting particle in this scattering experiment, it will easily pass through a static electron loop and give an experimental result that the electron radius is 0. So it's necessary to use the particle close to the measured electron energy as detection particle.

② Each matter particle loop formed by a circling photon is the elementary particle. Protons and neutrons are also the elementary particles, they should be formed by the photon loop with much higher frequency and much shorter loop radius. But any elementary particles can be collided into fragments and electromagnetic waves by the particles with similar loop radius and opposite charge. When the particles collide each other, the fragments and the energy released are only the redistribution of electromagnetic waves in loop or in line.

③ Positive and antimatter particles need the opposite charge and the same loop size. When they meet, their loop structures will be completely destroyed by the two waves with the opposite amplitudes and the same loop size, so that all the electromagnetic waves will escape together. For example, if there is a big energy difference between the electron and positron, they will not be a pair of antimatter particles because their loop size are much different. When they meet at this time, they will never annihilate and release energy. An electron with 20Gev energy and a rest positron with 511Kev will never annihilate when they collide.

7. Discussion before the End

If these predictions are proven in the future, our physical theory will become simple, the classical theory will also be able to explain and predict the quantum world. The only question is where the centripetal acceleration of circling photon comes from. This is a interesting question, which will lead to another question: why does matter particle generate? Maybe it's relative with quantum gravity or extra dimension or dark matter, which can unify the whole physical theory at last. But now, the most important thing is to make it sure that the centripetal acceleration capturing photon already exists in nature and the matter particle is really formed by the circling photon. These predictions in the paper can check whether it is true or not.

Founding

None.

Acknowledgments

Thank Mr. Hua Qingya, a senior optoelectronic engineer, for spending a lot of time to discuss such an amazing possibility with me and give me a lot of valuable advice.

References

Books

1. Ma Haiwu. Electromagnetic Field Theory (Tsinghua University Press, Beijing, 2016)
2. Liu Liao, Fei Baojun, Zhang Yunzhong. Special Relativity (Science Press, Beijing, 2008)
3. PAM Dirac. The Principles of Quantum Mechanics (Machinery Industry Press, Beijing, 2018)